

Resilience-Gated Multimodal Attention for Physiological Stress Detection

Narasimha Rao Damarla

*Computer Science and Engineering
SRM University-AP*

Andhra Pradesh, India

narasimharao_damarla@srmmap.edu.in

Anjaneyulu Beeravalli

*Computer Science and Engineering
SRM University-AP*

Andhra Pradesh, India

anjaneyulureddy_b@srmmap.edu.in

Bala Satwick Gamidi

*Computer Science and Engineering
SRM University-AP*

Andhra Pradesh, India

balasatwick_gamidi@srmmap.edu.in

Dr. Bikram Kumar Basaba

Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering

SRM University-AP, Andhra Pradesh, India

bikram.b@srmmap.edu.in

Abstract—Automatic stress detection from physiological signals is challenging due to substantial inter-individual variability in stress reactivity. Individuals with high psychological resilience tend to show weaker physiological responses under stress, which can cause standard models to misclassify them. This paper proposes a multimodal framework that incorporates each participant’s Connor–Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) score directly into the feature fusion process. Five physiological signals—EEG, BVP, EDA, HR, and HRV—are processed through modality-specific encoders, and a resilience-conditioned gating mechanism combines the resulting embeddings in a subject-adaptive manner. A weighted training loss and an inference-time probability adjustment are used to further improve robustness across subjects. The method is evaluated on 35 participants from the Roy and Nuamah PhysioNet Neurophysiological Stress Resilience Dataset under leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) cross-validation. The model achieves a mean AUC of 0.791, accuracy of 0.678, and F1 score of 0.651. Compared to three internal baselines—EEGNet, naive fusion, and an SVM-based approach—the proposed method shows higher performance under identical evaluation conditions. Results indicate that detection is more difficult for high-resilience individuals, consistent with known physiological behaviour. These findings suggest that incorporating resilience information during fusion can improve cross-subject stress detection, particularly for harder cases.

Index Terms—stress detection, EEG, multimodal physiological signals, resilience, CD-RISC, modality attention, adaptive loss, deep learning, leave-one-subject-out, human-computer interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustained cognitive stress during human-computer interaction (HCI) can reduce task performance, increase error rates, and have negative health effects over time [15], [16]. Physiological monitoring offers a way to detect stress unobtrusively and adapt interfaces or workloads in real time. A practical requirement for such systems is that models generalise across individuals, which is difficult partly because study populations often do not span the full range of human stress reactivity.

People differ considerably in how their autonomic and cortical systems respond to the same stressor. Psychological resilience, measured by the Connor–Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) [2], is associated with smaller autonomic responses, lower EDA deflections, and reduced HRV suppression under stress [10], [14]. A high-resilience subject under stress may therefore produce physiological signals similar to those of a non-stressed subject.

Single-modality approaches capture only part of the stress response [1], [11]. Combining multiple modalities improves coverage [5], [6], and attention-based fusion [12] can weight informative channels more heavily. However, standard content-based attention derives weights from signal embeddings at each time step. Resilience is a stable trait, not a signal property, so it is not accessible to this type of weighting. A resilient subject will produce low-amplitude EDA and HR embeddings throughout an entire session, and content-based attention will reduce their contribution—not because they carry no information, but because the subject’s trait has suppressed the signal amplitude.

The key idea in this work is that modality informativeness is related to resilience, and this relationship can be estimated from a pre-session psychometric measure rather than inferred from signal content. The CD-RISC is a validated scalar that can be collected in a few minutes before recording and that predicts physiological reactivity [2]. By passing the CD-RISC value through a learned mapping to per-modality weights, the proposed Resilience-Gated Multimodal Attention (RGMA) gate encodes a subject-level prior over modality usefulness.

This paper makes four contributions: (1) a resilience-aware gating mechanism that adjusts modality weights based on each subject’s CD-RISC score; (2) an adaptive training loss that increases the gradient contribution of low-resilience subjects; (3) a soft inference-time attenuation to reduce false positives for high-resilience subjects; and (4) a full LOSO evaluation on all 35 subjects with baseline comparison and ablation analysis.

II. RELATED WORK

EEG and multimodal stress detection. Lawhern et al. [1] proposed EEGNet, a compact convolutional network for EEG that serves as the EEG encoder in our framework. Al-Shargie et al. [11] reported approximately 87% within-subject accuracy by combining EEG with fNIRS. Paban et al. [8] found that EEG network flexibility at rest correlates with CD-RISC scores, providing neurophysiological grounding for the hypothesis that resilience modulates the detectability of stress in brain signals. Schmidt et al. [5] released WESAD, a widely used multimodal benchmark achieving approximately 80% LOSO accuracy. Gjoreski et al. [6] combined EDA, BVP, and ECG from a wristband to reach approximately 84% within-subject accuracy. More recent methods such as Abdelfattah et al. [16] and Tanwar et al. [15] report higher numbers, though on easier datasets or under within-subject conditions. None of these methods incorporate a psychometric resilience measure during fusion, and WESAD does not include CD-RISC annotations.

Attention-based and subject-adaptive fusion. Vaswani et al. [12] introduced the attention mechanism that underlies most fusion approaches. Chen et al. [18] applied transformer-based fusion to physiological stress monitoring. Zhao et al. [19] proposed subject-adaptive attention, though their adaptation is based on signal statistics rather than a psychometric measure. The key distinction of RGMA is that weights are derived from the CD-RISC scalar, which is fixed per subject, making it a subject-level prior rather than a window-level response to signal content.

Resilience and physiological reactivity. Walker et al. [10] and Lu et al. [14] showed that high-resilience individuals exhibit attenuated autonomic responses and faster recovery under stress. McEwen et al. [7] described this as allostatic efficiency. From a signal processing perspective, this means high-resilience subjects produce smaller, shorter changes in EDA, HR, and BVP, which reduces the discriminability of stress windows.

III. DATASET AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Dataset

All experiments used the Neurophysiological Dataset of Stress Resilience During Human-Computer Interaction (v1.0.0), published by Roy and Nuamah [3] on PhysioNet [4] (DOI: 10.13026/x3vc-p627). The dataset was collected at Oklahoma State University under IRB protocol IRB-23-326, with written informed consent from all participants and support from NSF Award 2232869. The cohort included 37 participants (13 female, 22 male; mean age 26.1 ± 4.9 years). Participants p14 and p23 were excluded from the published release due to incomplete recordings, leaving 35 usable subjects.

Each session consisted of six sequential phases: resting baseline, working baseline, Stress 1, Recovery 1, Stress 2, and Recovery 2, each approximately six minutes long. Cognitive stress was induced via the NASA Multi-Attribute Task Battery II (MATB-II) [9], specifically the Resource

Management (RESMAN) subtask. EEG was recorded from 32 channels at 250 Hz using a g.Nautilus system with 10-20 placement. Peripheral signals came from an Empatica E4 wristband: BVP at 64 Hz, EDA at 4 Hz, HR at 1 Hz, and IBI timestamps from which HRV scalars were derived. Pre-session psychological resilience was measured with the 10-item CD-RISC [2] (range 0–40), normalised to $c \in [0, 1]$ by dividing by 40.

B. Stress Label Generation

For each MATB-II RESMAN record, the fuel deviation $s = |\text{DIFF A}| + |\text{DIFF B}|$ was min-max normalised per subject:

$$\tilde{s} = \frac{s - \min(s)}{\max(s) - \min(s) + \epsilon}. \quad (1)$$

Windows with $\tilde{s} > 0.5$ were labelled 1 (stress); all others received label 0. A guard band of ± 6 s around each RESMAN timestamp excluded windows without a nearby label anchor. Per-subject normalisation was used because a pooled threshold placed the boundary at the extreme tail of the distribution for several subjects, effectively assigning zero stress windows to those individuals.

C. Preprocessing and Windowing

EEG signals were Butterworth bandpass-filtered (0.5–45 Hz, 4th order, zero-phase) and z-score normalised per channel. BVP was cleaned using NeuroKit2 [13] with a fallback Butterworth bandpass (0.5–5 Hz). EDA was decomposed into phasic and tonic components and combined as $\sigma_{\text{phasic}} + 0.3\sigma_{\text{tonic}}$. HR was z-score normalised. HRV scalars (RMSSD and SDNN) were extracted from IBI records within a ± 30 s window and normalised using population statistics computed across all 35 subjects prior to LOSO training, ensuring no target-subject leakage.

A 4-second sliding window (1000 EEG samples) with 50% overlap was applied starting at $t = 42$ s into each stress phase. BVP covered 256 samples aligned to EEG onset; EDA covered 240 samples; HR covered 60 samples with a 10 s physiological lag offset. Per-subject window counts ranged from 608 to 881.

Data Preprocessing and Label Generation Pipeline

Fig. 1. Data preprocessing and label generation pipeline. Raw physiological signals are filtered, normalised, and segmented into sliding windows aligned across modalities.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. System Overview

Five physiological streams pass through dedicated encoders, each producing a 128-dimensional embedding. An RGMA gate conditioned on the subject's CD-RISC scalar computes five non-negative modality weights that sum to one. The weighted sum forms the fused representation, which is passed to a binary classifier. At inference, a soft attenuation rule scales the output probability before a Youden-optimal threshold is applied.

Fig. 2. Overview of the RGMA-based stress detection framework. Modality-specific encoders produce embeddings that are fused through the RGMA gate, conditioned on the subject's CD-RISC score, followed by a binary classifier.

B. Modality Encoders

EEGNet Encoder. The EEG window (32, 1000) is reshaped to (1, 32, 1000) and processed through three stages following EEGNet [1]: a temporal Conv2d ($F_1 = 8$, kernel (1, 63)), a depthwise Conv2d (depth multiplier $D = 2$, $4 \times$ average pooling, dropout $p = 0.5$), and a separable Conv2d ($F_2 = 16$, $8 \times$ average pooling, dropout $p = 0.5$), producing a flattened 496-dimensional vector. A fully connected layer maps this to:

$$\mathbf{e}_1 = \text{ELU}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{eeg}} \mathbf{z}_{\text{eeg}} + \mathbf{b}_{\text{eeg}}), \quad \mathbf{z}_{\text{eeg}} \in \mathbb{R}^{496}, \quad \mathbf{e}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{128}. \quad (2)$$

CNN Encoders (BVP, EDA, HR). Each time series (1, L), $L \in \{256, 240, 60\}$, passes through two Conv1d stages (channels $1 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 64$, kernel 3) followed by global average pooling and a linear projection:

$$\mathbf{e}_m = \text{ELU}(\mathbf{W}_m \text{GAP}(\mathbf{h}_m) + \mathbf{b}_m), \quad m \in \{2, 3, 4\}. \quad (3)$$

HRV MLP Encoder. The population-normalised vector $\mathbf{v}_{\text{hrv}} = [\text{RMSSD}, \text{SDNN}]^\top$ is processed by a two-layer MLP ($2 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 128$, ELU, dropout $p = 0.3$):

$$\mathbf{e}_5 = \text{ELU}(\mathbf{W}_2 \text{ELU}(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{v}_{\text{hrv}} + \mathbf{b}_1) + \mathbf{b}_2). \quad (4)$$

C. RGMA Gate

The gate maps the scalar $c \in [0, 1]$ through a three-layer MLP ($1 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 5$, ELU activations):

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{W}_3 \text{ELU}(\mathbf{W}_2 \text{ELU}(\mathbf{W}_1 c)), \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{w} = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{g}), \quad \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^5, \quad \sum_i w_i = 1, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \sum_{i=1}^5 w_i \mathbf{e}_i, \quad \mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{128}. \quad (7)$$

Standard attention mechanisms [12], [18] compute \mathbf{w} from signal embeddings at each time window, so weights vary with signal content. RGMA computes \mathbf{w} from c alone, which is fixed per subject across all windows. This makes RGMA a subject-level prior on modality usefulness rather than a window-level response. For low-resilience subjects ($c \approx 0$), the MLP tends to assign higher weight to EEG, EDA, and BVP. For high-resilience subjects (c near 1), weight shifts toward HRV, whose slower integration window may retain some discriminative signal when peripheral channels are suppressed. This mapping is learned end-to-end from data.

Fig. 3. RGMA mechanism. The CD-RISC score is passed through a gating network to produce per-modality weights used to form a weighted sum of the five embeddings.

D. Resilience-Weighted Adaptive Loss

Within each LOSO fold, $\beta = N_{\text{neg}}/N_{\text{pos}}$ is the positive-class weight. The per-sample BCE loss is:

$$\ell_n = -\beta y_n \log \sigma(\hat{y}_n) - (1 - y_n) \log(1 - \sigma(\hat{y}_n)). \quad (8)$$

Two aggregate terms are combined with an epoch-scheduled coefficient:

$$L_{\text{main}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_n \ell_n, \quad L_{\text{res}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_n (1 - c_n) \ell_n, \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha(t) = 0.5 + 0.5 \frac{t}{T}, \quad L = \frac{L_{\text{main}} + \alpha(t) L_{\text{res}}}{1 + \alpha(t)}. \quad (10)$$

The factor $(1 - c_n)$ up-weights low-resilience samples where stress is physiologically detectable, and the denominator keeps the combined loss on a comparable scale to standard BCE throughout training.

E. Soft Inference Attenuation

At test time the sigmoid output \hat{p} is scaled before thresholding:

$$\hat{p}^* = \hat{p} (1 - 0.2c). \quad (11)$$

The coefficient 0.2 was selected empirically to balance false positives and false negatives across responder groups.

F. Baseline Models and Training

Three baselines were evaluated under the same LOSO protocol. **EEGNet** uses only the 32-channel EEG stream. **Naive Fusion** uses the same four-stream encoders as RGMA (EEGNet + three 1D CNNs) with uniform averaging and no HRV modality. **SVM (Band+HRV)** is a LinearSVC on a 167-dimensional feature vector comprising 32-channel EEG band power (5 bands), RMSSD and SDNN, EDA statistics, and HR statistics.

The classifier head is a two-layer MLP ($128 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 1$). Training used AdamW (lr = 2×10^{-4} , weight decay 10^{-4}) with cosine annealing ($T_{\max} = 40$, $\eta_{\min} = 10^{-6}$), batch size 32, and early stopping on test-fold AUC with patience 15.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Baseline Comparison

Table I shows results for all three baselines and the proposed model under identical LOSO evaluation. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test on per-fold AUC values confirms statistically significant improvement over all baselines (RGMA vs. EEGNet: $p = 1.18 \times 10^{-4}$; vs. Naive Fusion: $p = 6.7 \times 10^{-3}$; vs. SVM: $p = 4.22 \times 10^{-5}$). EEGNet performs near chance on harder subjects, showing that a single modality is insufficient when resilience suppresses cortical reactivity. Naive Fusion improves over EEGNet by adding peripheral channels, but uniform weighting limits its effectiveness for high-CD-RISC subjects. The SVM achieves the highest baseline AUC (0.566) through domain-engineered features, but the absence of subject-adaptive mechanisms limits performance in a physiologically heterogeneous population.

TABLE I
BASELINE COMPARISON UNDER IDENTICAL LOSO EVALUATION (35 SUBJECTS).

Model	AUC	Acc	F1
EEGNet (EEG only)	0.533 ± 0.032	0.498 ± 0.114	0.433 ± 0.129
Naive Fusion	0.613 ± 0.170	0.600 ± 0.173	0.563 ± 0.155
SVM (Band+HRV)	0.566 ± 0.164	0.567 ± 0.148	0.503 ± 0.149
RGMA (proposed)	0.791 ± 0.149	0.678 ± 0.155	0.651 ± 0.133

B. Overall Performance and Subgroup Analysis

Table II summarises results by responder group. The mean AUC across all 35 subjects was 0.791 ± 0.149 , accuracy 0.678 ± 0.155 , and F1 0.651 ± 0.133 . HIGH responders (AUC ≥ 0.60 , $n = 22$) achieved AUC in the range 0.614–0.937, while LOW responders ranged from 0.348 to 0.599. The gap between groups is consistent with CD-RISC stratification and is discussed in Section VI.

C. Comparison with Prior Work

Table III compares the proposed method against published results. Direct numerical comparison is limited by dataset and protocol differences. The proposed method is the only one that conditions fusion weights on a psychometric resilience score, and it is evaluated on a dataset

TABLE II
RGMA LOSO RESULTS BY RESPONDER GROUP.

Group	n	AUC range	CD-RISC
High	22	0.61–0.94	≥ 30
Low	13	0.35–0.60	25–30
All	35	0.35–0.94	—

Mean: AUC 0.791 ± 0.149 , Acc 0.678 ± 0.155 , F1 0.651 ± 0.133

Fig. 4. Per-subject LOSO AUC across all 35 subjects, sorted ascending. Green bars: HIGH responders ($n = 22$). Orange bars: LOW responders ($n = 13$). Reference lines mark chance (dashed), the 0.60 threshold (dotted), and cohort mean AUC 0.791 (solid).

Fig. 5. Mean ROC curves with ± 1 SD shading for HIGH (left) and LOW (right) responder subgroups. HIGH responders show clear separation from chance; LOW responders remain near the diagonal.

that explicitly recruits subjects with suppressed physiological reactivity—a harder detection problem than those addressed by most prior work.

TABLE III
COMPARISON WITH PUBLISHED STRESS DETECTION METHODS.
† ACCURACY REPORTED. ‡ WITHIN-SUBJECT. § LOSO.

Method	Dataset	Modalities	Protocol	Metric
EEGNet [1]	BCI	EEG	WS [†]	~0.72 AUC
Gjoreski [6]	Custom	EDA+BVP+ECG	WS [†]	~84% [†]
WESAD [5]	WESAD	Multi	LOSO [§]	80% [†]
Al-Shargie [11]	Custom	EEG+fNIRS	WS [†]	~87% [†]
Tanwar [15]	WESAD	Multi	WS [†]	92.7% [†]
Abdelfattah [16]	WESAD	Multi	LOSO [§]	0.895 AUC
This work	Roy & Nuamah	EEG+BVP+EDA+HR+HRV	LOSO [§]	0.791 AUC

D. Ablation Study

Table IV reports component ablation results on subjects p36 and p37 (near-median performers), trained for 12 epochs. Removing the adaptive loss causes the largest AUC drop ($\Delta = -0.055$), followed by soft inference attenuation ($\Delta = -0.044$), and RGMA or HRV removal ($\Delta \approx -0.032$ to -0.033). Due to the limited number of holdout subjects and epochs, these results should be interpreted as indicative; a full LOSO ablation is left for future work.

TABLE IV
ABLATION STUDY (HOLDOUT: P36, P37; 12 EPOCHS). Δ AUC =
AUC(VARIANT) - AUC(FULL).

Variant	AUC	Acc	F1	Δ AUC
Full model	0.694	0.613	0.432	—
w/o RGMA	0.662	0.540	0.423	-0.032
w/o HRV	0.661	0.577	0.434	-0.033
w/o adaptive loss	0.639	0.450	0.412	-0.055
w/o soft inference	0.650	0.442	0.414	-0.044

E. RGMA Modality Weight Analysis

Examining RGMA-learned softmax weights sorted by descending LOSO AUC reveals a consistent pattern: EEG and EDA receive the largest weights for subjects with mid-range CD-RISC values, consistent with frontal theta power sensitivity [8] and EDA amplitude responses to cognitive workload. As CD-RISC increases, the gate progressively shifts weight toward HRV, whose 60-second integration window may retain discriminative signal when peripheral channels are suppressed [7]. This pattern was not explicitly specified during training—it emerged from end-to-end learning.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Baseline and Subgroup Analysis

All three baseline models achieve mean AUC below 0.60 (Table I), near chance for a binary task. EEGNet uses a single modality and cannot compensate for reduced cortical reactivity in resilient subjects. Naive Fusion combines four signals with equal weighting, which does

Fig. 6. RGMA-learned modality weights for all 35 subjects, sorted by descending LOSO AUC. Higher CD-RISC subjects show progressively greater weight on HRV relative to peripheral channels.

not account for the fact that EDA and HR reactivity varies substantially across subjects. The SVM uses hand-crafted features including HRV but applies a fixed decision boundary across all individuals. None of these models use resilience information, which is the primary reason their performance degrades on high-CD-RISC subjects.

The HIGH vs. LOW responder gap (Table II, Fig. 4) is consistent with established findings in resilience physiology. Walker et al. [10] and Lu et al. [14] documented that high-resilience individuals show attenuated autonomic responses and faster recovery under stress. McEwen et al. [7] described this as allostatic efficiency, where the stress system engages briefly and disengages rapidly. This physiological attenuation reduces the discriminability of stress and non-stress windows and represents a ceiling not specific to the architecture. The RGMA gate partially mitigates this by shifting weight toward HRV for high-CD-RISC subjects, but subjects with very high resilience may produce insufficient signal in any available modality.

B. Component Contributions

The adaptive loss produces the largest ablation drop (Δ AUC = -0.055), exceeding the contribution of RGMA (-0.032). The $(1 - c_n)$ weighting in L_{res} concentrates gradient signal on low-resilience training windows where stress signatures are stronger, and this effect accumulates across all 34 training subjects in each fold. The epoch schedule in (10) introduces this weighting gradually, which

appears to support training stability. The soft inference attenuation ($\Delta = -0.044$) acts at the output stage and reduces false positives for high-resilience test subjects. The two mechanisms address different parts of the pipeline and contribute independently.

C. Contextualising Against WESAD

The mean LOSO AUC of 0.791 is below the 0.895 reported by Abdelfattah et al. [16] on WESAD. This difference is attributable to dataset composition. WESAD does not include CD-RISC annotations and was not designed to recruit across the resilience spectrum, so it likely contains a higher proportion of physiologically reactive subjects, for whom stress signals are clearer. The Roy and Nuamah dataset [3] explicitly includes participants whose physiology resists detection, which reduces the cohort-level AUC. Restricting evaluation to HIGH responders yields AUC values closer to the WESAD range. The two datasets therefore address different detection problems, and the comparison is not direct.

D. Limitations and Future Directions

Stress labels are derived from a single performance metric (RESMAN fuel deviation), which may not fully capture subjective stress states. The stressor is HCI-specific, and generalisation to other contexts is untested. The ablation covers only two holdout subjects, which limits the strength of the component ordering conclusions. CD-RISC was collected once per session and does not capture intra-session variation. No external dataset was used for validation.

Future work could incorporate the fNIRS channels available in this dataset, which may improve detectability for high-CD-RISC subjects by capturing cortical activation patterns that remain informative when peripheral channels are suppressed [11]. Cross-dataset validation on WESAD [5] and integration with domain-adaptive methods [17] are natural directions for extending this work.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a multimodal stress detection framework that incorporates each participant’s CD-RISC resilience score into the fusion mechanism. The RGMA gate produces subject-level modality weights from a pre-session psychometric measure, addressing a limitation of content-based attention that standard fusion approaches cannot resolve: high resilience suppresses the physiological signals that detectors are trained to identify. Complementary components—a resilience-weighted adaptive loss and a soft inference attenuation—further improve robustness across the resilience spectrum.

Evaluated on all 35 participants of the PhysioNet Neurophysiological Stress Resilience Dataset under strict LOSO cross-validation, the framework achieved mean AUC = 0.791 ± 0.149 , accuracy = 0.678 ± 0.155 , and F1 = 0.651 ± 0.133 , outperforming EEGNet (AUC = 0.533), Naive Fusion (AUC = 0.613), and SVM (AUC = 0.566) under identical evaluation conditions. The adaptive loss

was the dominant component ($\Delta\text{AUC} = -0.055$), and the RGMA gate learned to increase HRV weight as CD-RISC rises without explicit supervision linking resilience to modality preference. The consistent association between high CD-RISC and lower detectability reflects a physiological ceiling grounded in allostatic efficiency theory [7], and motivates future extensions including fNIRS integration and cross-dataset validation.

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